

Analysis for Wimmer, Whalley, Hollins memory paper.

18 Sept 2019

Setup

```
library(tidyverse)

## -- Attaching packages ---- tidyverse 1.2.1 --
## v ggplot2 3.2.0          v purrr  0.3.2
## v tibble  2.1.3          v dplyr  0.8.3
## v tidyr   0.8.3.9000     v stringr 1.4.0
## v readr   1.3.1          v forcats 0.4.0

## -- Conflicts ----- tidyverse_conflicts() --
## x dplyr::filter() masks stats::filter()
## x dplyr::lag()     masks stats::lag()

library(rstanarm)

## Loading required package: Rcpp
## Registered S3 method overwritten by 'xts':
##   method      from
##   as.zoo.xts  zoo
## rstanarm (Version 2.18.2, packaged: 2018-11-08 22:19:38 UTC)
## - Do not expect the default priors to remain the same in future rstanarm versions.
## Thus, R scripts should specify priors explicitly, even if they are just the defaults.
## - For execution on a local, multicore CPU with excess RAM we recommend calling
## options(mc.cores = parallel::detectCores())
## - Plotting theme set to bayesplot::theme_default().

library(pander)
library(tidybayes)
library(emmeans)
library(pacman)
library(coda)
library(bridgesampling)

options(mc.cores = parallel::detectCores()-1)
emm_options(summary = list(type = "response"))
ITER=10000
```

Import data

```
df <- foreign::read.spss('Combined.sav',
                        to.data.frame = T)
names(df) <- names(df) %>% tolower()
```

```

ages_levs <- df$age_group %>% unique
ages_labs <- c("7", "10", "A")

df <- df %>%
  # participant_id was messed up so we create a new one. data in original file sorted,
  # and each 4 rows=1 person
  mutate(person = sort(rep(1:400, 4))[1:n()]) %>%
  arrange(participant_id) %>%
  mutate(choice=ifelse(is.na(skip), "forced", "free")) %>%
  mutate(skip = ifelse(is.na(skip), 0, skip)) %>%
  select(-accuracy, -quantity) %>%
  select(person, condition, choice, itemtype, everything()) %>%
  # if participant skipped all trials we drop this row because binomial model can't cope
  # with zero-trials.
  # only 1 row affected
  filter(!(yes+no==0)) %>%
  # n = n_attempted
  mutate(n = yes+no) %>%
  # calculate n trials administered (i.e. ntrials in the design which is used as a divisor
  # in some of the calcs below)
  mutate(ntrials = yes+no+skip) %>%
  mutate(correct = ifelse(str_detect(itemtype, "Prese"), yes, no)) %>%
  # put a space inside labels
  mutate(itemtype = str_replace_all(itemtype, "([A-Z])", " \\1")) %>%
  # fix labels
  mutate(age_group = factor(age_group, levels=ages_levs, labels = ages_labs)) %>%
  mutate(choice=forcats::fct_relabel(choice, Hmisc::capitalize)) %>%
  mutate(condition=forcats::fct_recode(condition, "Shallow"="Incidental", "Standard"="Intentional"))

```

Plotting the raw data

```

angleplot.df.raw <- df %>%
  group_by(age_group, choice, itemtype) %>%
  summarise(
    q=mean(correct/(yes+no+skip)),
    a=mean(correct/(yes+no)) %>%
  ungroup()

angleplot.raw <- angleplot.df.raw %>%
  ggplot(aes(y=q, x=a, color=choice, group=age_group)) +
  geom_abline(intercept = 0, slope=1, alpha=1, linetype="dotted") +
  geom_line(color="darkgrey") +
  geom_hline(data = angleplot.df.raw %>% filter(choice=="Forced"),
    aes(yintercept = a), alpha=1, linetype="dotted") +
  geom_point() +
  xlab('Accuracy') +
  ylab('Quantity') +
  facet_grid(itemtype~age_group, scales="fixed")
angleplot.raw

```


Skipping rates

Figure 1.

```
ts = element_text(size=10.5)
tsm = element_text(size=9.5)
df %>%
```

```

mutate(Condition=condition) %>%
filter(choice=="Free") %>%
ggplot(aes(age_group, skip/ntrials,
           group=Condition, shape=Condition, linetype=Condition)) +
stat_summary(geom="line", alpha=.6, fun.data = mean_se,
             position=position_dodge(width=.1)) +
stat_summary(fun.data = mean_cl_boot, position=position_dodge(width=.1)) +
facet_grid(.~itemtype) +
ylab("p(skipped)") +
scale_linetype_discrete("") +
scale_color_discrete("", guide=F) +
scale_shape_discrete("") +
xlab("Age group") +
theme(legend.text=ts, axis.text =ts , axis.title=ts, strip.text=tsm, legend.position="bottom")

```



```

ggsave('figure1.pdf', width = 7, height=2.5)

```

“Next, it was investigated whether there were any differences in the number of presented items, critical lures, related distractors, unrelated distractors skipped...”

Select data (used below too)

```

skipdf <- df %>% filter(choice=="Free")

```

Run the model, save chains (output not shown):

```

mskip <- rstanarm::stan_glmer(cbind(skip, ntrials) ~ age_group * itemtype * condition + (1|person),
                             family=binomial(), data=skipdf, chains=3, iter=ITER)
write_rds(mskip, 'mskip.rstanarm.RDS')

```

Read chains back (so this file can run without refitting models):

```

mskip <- read_rds('mskip.rstanarm.RDS')

```

Note we used default rstanarm priors (zero centered but weakly informative):

```

prior_summary(mskip)

```

```

## Priors for model 'mskip'
## -----
## Intercept (after predictors centered)

```

```

## ~ normal(location = 0, scale = 10)
##
## Coefficients
## ~ normal(location = [0,0,0,...], scale = [2.5,2.5,2.5,...])
##
## Covariance
## ~ decov(reg. = 1, conc. = 1, shape = 1, scale = 1)
## -----
## See help('prior_summary.stanreg') for more details

```

Check neff and rhat for convergence... no output is a good thing:

```

summary(mskip) %>% as.data.frame() %>%
  rownames_to_column('term') %>%
  select(term, mean, mcse, n_eff, Rhat) %>%
  filter(n_eff<1000 | Rhat>1.005)

```

```

## [1] term mean mcse n_eff Rhat
## <0 rows> (or 0-length row.names)

```

Skipping rates were substantially above zero:

```

emmeans(mskip, ~1) %>%
  as_tibble() %>%
  mutate_if(is.numeric, ~sprintf("%.2f", .*100)) %>%
  rename(percent=prob) %>%
  mutate(res_string = paste0(percent, " [", lower.HPD, " to ", upper.HPD, "]")) %>%
  pander()

```

1	percent	lower.HPD	upper.HPD	res_string
overall	7.42	5.89	9.06	7.42 [5.89 to 9.06]

Rates of skipping by item type

```

emmeans(mskip, "itemtype") %>%
  as_tibble() %>%
  mutate_if(is.numeric, ~sprintf("%.2f", .*100)) %>%
  rename(percent=prob) %>%
  mutate(res_string = paste0(percent, "% [", lower.HPD, " to ", upper.HPD, "]")) %>%
  select(itemtype, res_string) %>%
  pander()

```

NOTE: Results may be misleading due to involvement in interactions

itemtype	res_string
Critical Lures	8.08% [6.07 to 10.19]
Presented Items	6.38% [5.01 to 7.89]
Related Distractors	9.12% [6.90 to 11.38]
Unrelated Distractors	6.41% [4.76 to 8.26]

More related distractors were skipped than all other items (compares each itemtype with the average of the others):

```
contrast(emmeans(mskip, "itemtype"), method="del.eff") %>%
  as_tibble() %>%
  mutate_if(is.numeric, ~sprintf("%.2f", .)) %>%
  mutate(res_string = paste0("OR = ", odds.ratio,
                             " [", lower.HPD, " to ", upper.HPD, "]")) %>%
  select(contrast, res_string) %>%
  pander()
```

NOTE: Results may be misleading due to involvement in interactions

contrast	res_string
Critical Lures effect	OR = 1.13 [0.92 to 1.36]
Presented Items effect	OR = 0.81 [0.69 to 0.93]
Related Distractors effect	OR = 1.35 [1.10 to 1.62]
Unrelated Distractors effect	OR = 0.81 [0.64 to 0.99]

There was also an effect of age group

```
contrast(emmeans(mskip, "age_group"), method="revpairwise") %>%
  as_tibble() %>%
  mutate_if(is.numeric, ~sprintf("%.2f", .)) %>%
  mutate(res_string = paste0("OR = ", odds.ratio,
                             " [", lower.HPD, " to ", upper.HPD, "]")) %>%
  select(contrast, res_string) %>%
  pander()
```

NOTE: Results may be misleading due to involvement in interactions

contrast	res_string
10 / 7	OR = 1.12 [0.63 to 1.74]
A / 7	OR = 3.25 [1.79 to 5.26]
A / 10	OR = 2.92 [1.54 to 4.84]

```
contrast(emmeans(mskip, "condition"), method="revpairwise") %>%
  as_tibble() %>%
  mutate_if(is.numeric, ~sprintf("%.2f", .)) %>%
  mutate(res_string = paste0("OR = ", odds.ratio,
                             " [", lower.HPD, " to ", upper.HPD, "]")) %>%
  select(contrast, res_string) %>%
  pander()
```

NOTE: Results may be misleading due to involvement in interactions

contrast	res_string
Shallow / Standard	OR = 0.65 [0.39 to 0.95]

“Effect of reporting on accuracy ...”

Fit the models, with and without condition and it’s interactions included, the compute the BF:

```

ITER <- 20000 # more iters for bridge sampling below
m.cond.h0 <- rstanarm::stan_glmer(cbind(correct, ntrials-correct) ~
                                age_group * itemtype * choice + condition + (1|person),
                                family=binomial(),
                                data=df,
                                chains=3,
                                iter=ITER,
                                diagnostic_file = file.path(tempdir(), "dfh0.csv"))

m.cond.h1 <- rstanarm::stan_glmer(cbind(correct, ntrials-correct) ~
                                age_group * itemtype * choice * condition + (1|person),
                                family=binomial(),
                                data=df,
                                chains=3,
                                iter=ITER,
                                diagnostic_file = file.path(tempdir(), "dfh1.csv"))

write_rds(m.cond.h0, 'm.cond.h0.rds')
write_rds(m.cond.h1, 'm.cond.h1.rds')

# Compute the Bayes Factor
bridge_h0 <- bridge_sampler(m.cond.h0,
                            method = "normal",
                            repetitions = 100,
                            cores=8,
                            silent=T)

bridge_h1 <- bridge_sampler(m.cond.h1,
                            method = "normal",
                            repetitions = 100,
                            cores=8,
                            silent=T)

bf01 <- bf(bridge_h0, bridge_h1)
write_rds(bf01, 'bf01.rds')

```

The Bayes factor in favour of the null hypothesis (no effect of encoding condition) was...

```

bf01 <- read_rds('bf01.rds')
bf01

## Estimated Bayes factor (based on medians of log marginal likelihood estimates)
## in favor of bridge_h0 over bridge_h1: 57624.24781
## Range of estimates: 41099.36788 to 82111.05482
## Interquartile range: 10241.86608

# use the full model from now on, but marginalise across conditions
m <- read_rds('m.cond.h1.rds')

```

Note default priors:

```

prior_summary(m)

## Priors for model 'm'
## -----
## Intercept (after predictors centered)

```

```

## ~ normal(location = 0, scale = 10)
##
## Coefficients
## ~ normal(location = [0,0,0,...], scale = [2.5,2.5,2.5,...])
##
## Covariance
## ~ decov(reg. = 1, conc. = 1, shape = 1, scale = 1)
## -----
## See help('prior_summary.stanreg') for more details

```

Figure 2 and related text

“Consequently, in our subsequent analysis, we report the results collapsed across encoding conditions (although our data supplement provides additional plots and tables split by condition) ...”

Check neff and rhat for convergence - no output is good here

```

summary(m) %>% as.data.frame() %>%
  rownames_to_column('term') %>%
  select(term, mean, mcse, n_eff, Rhat) %>%
  filter(n_eff<1000 | Rhat>1.005)

```

```

## [1] term mean mcse n_eff Rhat
## <0 rows> (or 0-length row.names)

```

Figure 2 (first half)

```

choice.effect.by.ages <- contrast(
  emmeans(m, ~choice|age_group|itemtype, transform="log"),
  method="pairwise") %>% as_tibble()

```

NOTE: Results may be misleading due to involvement in interactions

```

fig2 <- choice.effect.by.ages %>%
  ggplot(aes(age_group, ratio, ymin=lower.HPD, ymax=upper.HPD)) +
  geom_pointrange() +
  facet_grid(itemtype~.) +
  geom_hline(yintercept = 1) +
  xlab("Age group") +
  ylab("Odds ratio\n(benefit of skipping)")
ggsave('figure2.pdf',fig2, width=2.5, height=8)
fig2

```


Odds ratios for the text following:

```
contrast(
  emmeans(m, ~choice|age_group|itemtype, transform="log"),
  method="pairwise") %>% as_tibble() %>%
  mutate_if(is.numeric, ~sprintf("%.2f", .)) %>%
```

```
mutate(res_string = paste0("OR = ", ratio,
                           " [" , lower.HPD, " to " , upper.HPD, "]" )) %>%
select(age_group, itemtype, res_string) %>%
pander(caption="Effect of choice on accuracy.")
```

NOTE: Results may be misleading due to involvement in interactions

Table 6: Effect of choice on accuracy.

age_group	itemtype	res_string
7	Critical Lures	OR = 1.56 [1.34 to 1.79]
10	Critical Lures	OR = 1.24 [1.03 to 1.46]
A	Critical Lures	OR = 1.23 [0.86 to 1.68]
7	Presented Items	OR = 1.00 [0.93 to 1.08]
10	Presented Items	OR = 1.15 [1.07 to 1.24]
A	Presented Items	OR = 1.21 [1.12 to 1.32]
7	Related Distractors	OR = 1.16 [1.08 to 1.25]
10	Related Distractors	OR = 1.12 [1.04 to 1.21]
A	Related Distractors	OR = 1.42 [1.22 to 1.67]
7	Unrelated Distractors	OR = 1.13 [1.06 to 1.20]
10	Unrelated Distractors	OR = 1.09 [1.03 to 1.15]
A	Unrelated Distractors	OR = 1.35 [1.23 to 1.49]

Additional plot split by condition promised by the text:

```
choice.effect.by.ages.conditions <- contrast(
  emmeans(m, ~choice|age_group|condition|itemtype, transform="response"),
  method="pairwise") %>% as_tibble()

choice.effect.by.ages.conditions %>%
ggplot(aes(age_group, estimate, ymin=lower.HPD, ymax=upper.HPD)) +
geom_pointrange() +
facet_grid(condition~itemtype) +
geom_hline(yintercept = 0) +
xlab("Age group") +
theme(legend.text=ts, axis.text = ts,
      axis.title=ts, strip.text=tsm, legend.position="bottom") +
ylab("Effect of skipping\nnon p(correct)")
```


Pairwise comparisons between age groups

Odds ratios from the text:

```
age.comparisons <- emmeans(m, ~choice*age_group|itemtype, transform="log") %>%
  contrast(method="pairwise", simple="choice") %>%
  contrast(simple="age_group", method="revpairwise") %>%
  as_tibble()
```

NOTE: Results may be misleading due to involvement in interactions

```
age.comparisons %>%
  mutate_if(is.numeric, ~sprintf("%.2f", .)) %>%
  mutate(res_string = paste0("OR = ", ratio,
    " [" , lower.HPD, " to " , upper.HPD, "]" )) %>%
  select(-ratio, -contrast, -lower.HPD, -upper.HPD) %>%
  pander()
```

contrast1	itemtype	res_string
10 / 7	Critical Lures	OR = 0.80 [0.63 to 0.98]
A / 7	Critical Lures	OR = 0.79 [0.54 to 1.11]
A / 10	Critical Lures	OR = 1.00 [0.65 to 1.40]
10 / 7	Presented Items	OR = 1.15 [1.03 to 1.28]
A / 7	Presented Items	OR = 1.21 [1.08 to 1.36]
A / 10	Presented Items	OR = 1.05 [0.94 to 1.17]
10 / 7	Related Distractors	OR = 0.96 [0.87 to 1.07]
A / 7	Related Distractors	OR = 1.23 [1.02 to 1.45]
A / 10	Related Distractors	OR = 1.27 [1.06 to 1.51]
10 / 7	Unrelated Distractors	OR = 0.97 [0.89 to 1.05]
A / 7	Unrelated Distractors	OR = 1.20 [1.07 to 1.35]
A / 10	Unrelated Distractors	OR = 1.24 [1.11 to 1.39]

```

fig3 <- age.comparisons %>%
  ggplot(aes(contrast1, ratio)) +
  geom_pointrange(aes(ymin=lower.HPD, ymax=upper.HPD)) +
  facet_grid(itemtype~.) +
  geom_hline(yintercept = 1) + coord_flip() +
  xlab("Comparison") + ylab("Odds Ratio") +
  theme(legend.text=ts, axis.text =ts , axis.title=ts, strip.text=tsm)

```

fig3


```

ggsave("figure3.pdf", fig3, width=3, height=5)

```

Combined figure to save space

```
pcomb <- gridExtra::grid.arrange(  
  fig2 +  
    ggtitle("A") +  
    theme(strip.background = element_blank(), strip.text = element_blank()),  
  fig3 +  
    ggtitle("B") + xlab(""),  
  ncol=2)
```



```
ggsave('figure2plus.pdf', pcomb, width=6, height=8)
```

Software citations

```
citation('rstanarm')
```

```
##
## To cite rstanarm in publications please use the first citation
## entry. If you were using the 'stan_jm' modelling function then,
## where possible, please consider including the second citation
## entry as well.
##
## Goodrich B, Gabry J, Ali I & Brilleman S. (2018). rstanarm:
## Bayesian applied regression modeling via Stan. R package version
## 2.17.4. http://mc-stan.org/.
##
## Brilleman SL, Crowther MJ, Moreno-Betancur M, Buros Novik J &
## Wolfe R. Joint longitudinal and time-to-event models via Stan.
## StanCon 2018. 10-12 Jan 2018. Pacific Grove, CA, USA.
## https://github.com/stan-dev/stancon\_talks/
##
## To see these entries in BibTeX format, use 'print(<citation>,
## bibtex=TRUE)', 'toBibtex(.)', or set
## 'options(citation.bibtex.max=999)'
```

```
citation('emmeans')
```

```
##
## To cite package 'emmeans' in publications use:
##
## Russell Lenth (2019). emmeans: Estimated Marginal Means, aka
## Least-Squares Means. R package version 1.4.0.009996.
## https://github.com/rvlenth/emmeans
##
## A BibTeX entry for LaTeX users is
##
## @Manual{,
##   title = {emmeans: Estimated Marginal Means, aka Least-Squares Means},
##   author = {Russell Lenth},
##   year = {2019},
##   note = {R package version 1.4.0.009996},
##   url = {https://github.com/rvlenth/emmeans},
## }
```

Versions for reproducibility

```
purrr::map(pacman::p_loaded(), p_info)
```

```
## [[1]]
## Package: bridgesampling
## Type: Package
## Title: Bridge Sampling for Marginal Likelihoods and Bayes Factors
## Version: 0.6-0
## Authors@R: c(person(given="Quentin F.", family="Gronau",
```

```

##       role=c("aut", "cre"), email="Quentin.F.Gronau@gmail.com",
##       comment=c(ORCID="0000-0001-5510-6943")),
##       person(given="Henrik", family="Singmann", role="aut",
##       comment=c(ORCID="0000-0002-4842-3657")),
##       person(given="Jonathan J.", family="Forster", role="ctb"),
##       person(given="Eric-Jan", family="Wagenmakers", role="ths"),
##       person(family="The JASP Team", role="ctb"),
##       person("Jiqiang", "Guo", role = "ctb"), person("Jonah",
##       "Gabry", role = "ctb"), person("Ben", "Goodrich", role =
##       c("ctb")), person("Kees", "Mulder", role = c("ctb")),
##       person("Perry", "de Valpine", role = c("ctb")) )
## Depends: R (>= 3.0.0)
## Imports: mvtnorm, Matrix, Brodningnag, stringr, coda, parallel,
##       scales, utils, methods
## Suggests: testthat, Rcpp, RcppEigen, R2jags, rjags, runjags,
##       knitr, rmarkdown, R.rsp, BayesFactor, rstan, rstanarm,
##       nimble, MCMCpack
## Description: Provides functions for estimating marginal
##       likelihoods, Bayes factors, posterior model probabilities,
##       and normalizing constants in general, via different
##       versions of bridge sampling (Meng & Wong, 1996,
##       <http://www3.stat.sinica.edu.tw/statistica/j6n4/j6n43/j6n43.htm>).
## License: GPL (>= 2)
## LazyData: true
## RoxygenNote: 6.1.0
## VignetteBuilder: knitr, R.rsp
## URL: https://github.com/quentingronau/bridgesampling
## NeedsCompilation: no
## Packaged: 2018-10-21 13:22:13 UTC; henrik
## Author: Quentin F. Gronau [aut, cre]
##       (<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5510-6943>), Henrik Singmann
##       [aut] (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4842-3657>), Jonathan
##       J. Forster [ctb], Eric-Jan Wagenmakers [ths], The JASP Team
##       [ctb], Jiqiang Guo [ctb], Jonah Gabry [ctb], Ben Goodrich
##       [ctb], Kees Mulder [ctb], Perry de Valpine [ctb]
## Maintainer: Quentin F. Gronau <Quentin.F.Gronau@gmail.com>
## Repository: CRAN
## Date/Publication: 2018-10-21 21:20:03 UTC
## Built: R 3.6.1; ; 2019-07-15 13:06:53 UTC; unix
##
## -- File: /usr/local/lib/R/site-library/bridgesampling/Meta/package.rds
##
## [[2]]
## Package: coda
## Version: 0.19-3
## Date: 2019-07-05
## Title: Output Analysis and Diagnostics for MCMC
## Authors@R: c(person("Martyn", "Plummer",
##       role=c("aut","cre","trl"),
##       email="martyn.plummer@gmail.com"), person("Nicky", "Best",
##       role="aut"), person("Kate", "Cowles", role="aut"),
##       person("Karen", "Vines", role="aut"), person("Deepayan",
##       "Sarkar", role="aut"), person("Douglas", "Bates",
##       role="aut"), person("Russell", "Almond", role="aut"),

```

```

##      person("Arni", "Magnusson", role="aut"))
## Depends: R (>= 2.14.0)
## Imports: lattice
## Description: Provides functions for summarizing and plotting the
##      output from Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) simulations, as
##      well as diagnostic tests of convergence to the equilibrium
##      distribution of the Markov chain.
## License: GPL (>= 2)
## NeedsCompilation: no
## Packaged: 2019-07-05 12:32:44 UTC; martyn
## Author: Martyn Plummer [aut, cre, trl], Nicky Best [aut], Kate
##      Cowles [aut], Karen Vines [aut], Deepayan Sarkar [aut],
##      Douglas Bates [aut], Russell Almond [aut], Arni Magnusson
##      [aut]
## Maintainer: Martyn Plummer <martyn.plummer@gmail.com>
## Repository: CRAN
## Date/Publication: 2019-07-05 13:30:03 UTC
## Built: R 3.6.1; ; 2019-07-15 14:00:44 UTC; unix
##
## -- File: /usr/local/lib/R/site-library/coda/Meta/package.rds
##
## [[3]]
## Package: pacman
## Type: Package
## Title: Package Management Tool
## Version: 0.5.1
## Authors@R: c(person("Tyler", "Rinker", role = c("aut", "cre",
##      "ctb"), email = "tyler.rinker@gmail.com"), person("Dason",
##      "Kurkiewicz", role = c("aut", "ctb"), email =
##      "dasonk@gmail.com"), person("Keith", "Hughitt", role =
##      c("ctb")), person("Albert", "Wang", role = c("ctb")),
##      person("Garrick", "Aden-Buie", role = c("ctb")),
##      person("Albert", "Wang", role = c("ctb")), person("Lukas",
##      "Burk", role = c("ctb")))
## Depends: R (>= 3.5.0)
## Imports: remotes, methods, stats, utils
## Suggests: BiocManager, knitr, lattice, testthat (>= 0.9.0), XML
## BugReports: https://github.com/trinker/pacman/issues?state=open
## Description: Tools to more conveniently perform tasks associated
##      with add-on packages. pacman conveniently wraps library and
##      package related functions and names them in an intuitive
##      and consistent fashion. It seeks to combine functionality
##      from lower level functions which can speed up workflow.
## License: GPL-2
## URL: https://github.com/trinker/pacman
## RoxygenNote: 6.1.1
## NeedsCompilation: no
## Packaged: 2019-03-11 01:37:03 UTC; trinker
## Author: Tyler Rinker [aut, cre, ctb], Dason Kurkiewicz [aut, ctb],
##      Keith Hughitt [ctb], Albert Wang [ctb], Garrick Aden-Buie
##      [ctb], Albert Wang [ctb], Lukas Burk [ctb]
## Maintainer: Tyler Rinker <tyler.rinker@gmail.com>
## Repository: CRAN
## Date/Publication: 2019-03-11 11:50:07 UTC

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## Built: R 3.6.1; ; 2019-08-16 13:37:14 UTC; unix
##
## -- File: /home/ben/R/x86_64-pc-linux-gnu-library/3.6/pacman/Meta/package.rds
##
## [[4]]
## Package: emmeans
## Type: Package
## Title: Estimated Marginal Means, aka Least-Squares Means
## Version: 1.4.0.009996
## Date: 2019-08-15
## Authors@R: c(person("Russell", "Lenth", role = c("aut", "cre",
##      "cph"), email = "russell-lenth@uiowa.edu"),
##      person("Henrik", "Singmann", role = "ctb"),
##      person("Jonathon", "Love", role = "ctb"), person("Paul",
##      "Buerkner", role = "ctb"), person("Maxime", "Herve", role =
##      "ctb"))
## Depends: R (>= 3.2)
## Imports: estimability (>= 1.3), graphics, methods, numDeriv,
##      stats, utils, plyr, mvtnorm, xtable (>= 1.8-2)
## Suggests: bayesplot, biglm, brms, car, coda (>= 0.17), ggplot2,
##      lattice, mediation, mgcv, multcomp, multcompView, nlme,
##      ordinal (>= 2014.11-12), pbkrtest (>= 0.4-1), lme4,
##      lmerTest (>= 2.0.32), MASS, MuMIn, rsm, knitr, rmarkdown,
##      scales, testthat
## Enhances: CARBayes, coxme, gee, geepack, MCMCglmm, MCMCpack, mice,
##      nnet, pscl, rstanarm, sommer, survival
## URL: https://github.com/rvlenth/emmeans
## BugReports: https://github.com/rvlenth/emmeans/issues
## LazyData: yes
## ByteCompile: yes
## Description: Obtain estimated marginal means (EMMs) for many
##      linear, generalized linear, and mixed models. Compute
##      contrasts or linear functions of EMMs, trends, and
##      comparisons of slopes. Plots and other displays.
##      Least-squares means are discussed, and the term "estimated
##      marginal means" is suggested, in Searle, Speed, and
##      Milliken (1980) Population marginal means in the linear
##      model: An alternative to least squares means, The American
##      Statistician 34(4), 216-221
##      <doi:10.1080/00031305.1980.10483031>.
## License: GPL-2 | GPL-3
## Encoding: UTF-8
## RoxygenNote: 6.1.1
## VignetteBuilder: knitr
## RemoteType: github
## RemoteHost: api.github.com
## RemoteRepo: emmeans
## RemoteUsername: rvlenth
## RemoteRef: master
## RemoteSha: c09cc9c34eaf062deb217cedbf5bd42318db304d
## GithubRepo: emmeans
## GithubUsername: rvlenth
## GithubRef: master
## GithubSHA1: c09cc9c34eaf062deb217cedbf5bd42318db304d

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## NeedsCompilation: no
## Packaged: 2019-08-16 09:52:16 UTC; ben
## Author: Russell Lenth [aut, cre, cph], Henrik Singmann [ctb],
##         Jonathon Love [ctb], Paul Buerkner [ctb], Maxime Herve
##         [ctb]
## Maintainer: Russell Lenth <russell-lenth@uiowa.edu>
## Built: R 3.6.1; ; 2019-08-16 09:52:16 UTC; unix
##
## -- File: /home/ben/R/x86_64-pc-linux-gnu-library/3.6/emmeans/Meta/package.rds
##
## [[5]]
## Package: tidybayes
## Title: Tidy Data and 'Geoms' for Bayesian Models
## Version: 1.1.0
## Date: 2019-06-02
## Authors@R: c( person("Matthew", "Kay", role = c("aut", "cre"),
##                   email = "mjskay@umich.edu"), person("Timothy", "Mastny",
##                   role = "ctb", email = "tim.mastny@gmail.com") )
## Maintainer: Matthew Kay <mjskay@umich.edu>
## Description: Compose data for and extract, manipulate, and
##              visualize posterior draws from Bayesian models ('JAGS',
##              'Stan', 'rstanarm', 'brms', 'MCMCglmm', 'coda', ...) in a
##              tidy data format. Functions are provided to help extract
##              tidy data frames of draws from Bayesian models and that
##              generate point summaries and intervals in a tidy format. In
##              addition, 'ggplot2' 'geoms' and 'stats' are provided for
##              common visualization primitives like points with multiple
##              uncertainty intervals, eye plots (intervals plus
##              densities), and fit curves with multiple, arbitrary
##              uncertainty bands.
## Depends: R (>= 3.5.0)
## Imports: plyr, dplyr (>= 0.8.0), tidyr, ggplot2 (>= 3.0.0), coda,
##          purrr (>= 0.2.3), rlang (>= 0.3.0), ggstance, grid,
##          forcats, HDInterval, arrayhelpers, tidyselect, tibble,
##          magrittr
## Suggests: knitr, testthat, vdiffr (>= 0.3.0), svglite, rstan (>=
##          2.17.0), runjags, rjags, jagsUI, rstanarm (>= 2.18.2),
##          emmeans, broom (>= 0.4.3), dotwhisker, MCMCglmm, bayesplot,
##          modelr, brms (>= 2.9.0), cowplot, ggribes, covr, gdtools,
##          rmarkdown, ggrepel, bindrcpp, RColorBrewer, ganimate,
##          gifski, png, transformr
## License: GPL (>= 3)
## Language: en-US
## BugReports: https://github.com/mjskay/tidybayes/issues/new
## URL: http://mjskay.github.io/tidybayes,
##       https://github.com/mjskay/tidybayes
## VignetteBuilder: knitr
## RoxygenNote: 6.1.1
## LazyData: true
## Encoding: UTF-8
## NeedsCompilation: no
## Packaged: 2019-06-02 20:30:28 UTC; matth
## Author: Matthew Kay [aut, cre], Timothy Mastny [ctb]
## Repository: CRAN

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## Date/Publication: 2019-06-02 21:10:03 UTC
## Built: R 3.6.1; ; 2019-07-17 08:38:11 UTC; unix
##
## -- File: /home/ben/R/x86_64-pc-linux-gnu-library/3.6/tidybayes/Meta/package.rds
##
## [[6]]
## Package: pander
## Authors@R: c( person("Gergely", "Daróczi", ,
##      "daroczig@rapporter.net", role = c("aut", "cre"), comment =
##      c(ORCID = "0000-0003-3149-8537")), person("Roman",
##      "Tsegelskyi", , "roman.tsegelskyi@gmail.com", role =
##      c("aut")))
## Title: An R 'Pandoc' Writer
## Type: Package
## Encoding: UTF-8
## Description: Contains some functions catching all messages,
##      'stdout' and other useful information while evaluating R
##      code and other helpers to return user specified text
##      elements (like: header, paragraph, table, image, lists
##      etc.) in 'pandoc' markdown or several type of R objects
##      similarly automatically transformed to markdown format.
##      Also capable of exporting/converting (the resulting)
##      complex 'pandoc' documents to e.g. HTML, 'PDF', 'docx' or
##      'odt'. This latter reporting feature is supported in brew
##      syntax or with a custom reference class with a smarty
##      caching 'backend'.
## Version: 0.6.3
## Date: 2018-11-06
## URL: http://rapporter.github.io/pander
## BugReports: https://github.com/rapporter/pander/issues
## License: AGPL-3 | file LICENSE
## Depends: R (>= 2.15.0)
## Imports: grDevices, graphics, methods, utils, stats, digest,
##      tools, Rcpp
## Suggests: grid, lattice, ggplot2 (>= 0.9.2), syilly, syilly.en,
##      futile.logger, survival, microbenchmark, zoo, nlme, descr,
##      MASS, knitr, rmarkdown, tables, reshape, memisc, Epi,
##      randomForest, tseries, gtable, rms, forecast, data.table
## SystemRequirements: pandoc (http://johnmacfarlane.net/pandoc) for
##      exporting markdown files to other formats.
## LinkingTo: Rcpp
## VignetteBuilder: knitr
## RoxygenNote: 6.1.0
## NeedsCompilation: yes
## Packaged: 2018-11-06 10:17:46 UTC; daroczig
## Author: Gergely Daróczi [aut, cre]
##      (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3149-8537>), Roman Tsegelskyi
##      [aut]
## Maintainer: Gergely Daróczi <daroczig@rapporter.net>
## Repository: CRAN
## Date/Publication: 2018-11-06 10:50:02 UTC
## Built: R 3.6.1; x86_64-pc-linux-gnu; 2019-07-15 14:12:53 UTC; unix
##
## -- File: /usr/local/lib/R/site-library/pander/Meta/package.rds

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##
## [[7]]
## Package: rstanarm
## Type: Package
## Title: Bayesian Applied Regression Modeling via Stan
## Version: 2.18.2
## Date: 2018-11-08
## Authors@R: c(person("Jonah", "Gabry", email =
##   "jsg2201@columbia.edu", role = "aut"), person("Imad",
##   "Ali", role = "ctb"), person("Sam", "Brilleman", role =
##   "ctb"), person(given = "Jacqueline Buros", family =
##   "Novik", role = "ctb", comment = "R/stan_jm.R"),
##   person("AstraZeneca", role = "ctb", comment =
##   "R/stan_jm.R"), person("Trustees of", "Columbia
##   University", role = "cph"), person("Simon", "Wood", role =
##   "cph", comment = "R/stan_gamm4.R"), person("R Core",
##   "Development Team", role = "cph", comment = "R/stan_aov.R"),
##   person("Douglas", "Bates", role = "cph", comment =
##   "R/pp_data.R"), person("Martin", "Maechler", role = "cph",
##   comment = "R/pp_data.R"), person("Ben", "Bolker", role =
##   "cph", comment = "R/pp_data.R"), person("Steve", "Walker",
##   role = "cph", comment = "R/pp_data.R"), person("Brian",
##   "Ripley", role = "cph", comment = "R/stan_aov.R,
##   R/stan_polr.R"), person("William", "Venables", role =
##   "cph", comment = "R/stan_polr.R"), person("Paul-Christian",
##   "Burkner", email = "paul.buerkner@gmail.com", role = "cph",
##   comment = "R/misc.R"), person("Ben", "Goodrich", email =
##   "benjamin.goodrich@columbia.edu", role = c("cre", "aut")))
## Description: Estimates previously compiled regression models using
##   the 'rstan' package, which provides the R interface to the
##   Stan C++ library for Bayesian estimation. Users specify
##   models via the customary R syntax with a formula and
##   data.frame plus some additional arguments for priors.
## License: GPL (>= 3)
## Depends: R (>= 3.4.0), Rcpp (>= 0.12.0), methods
## Imports: bayesplot (>= 1.5.0), ggplot2 (>= 2.2.1), lme4 (>=
##   1.1-8), loo (>= 2.0.0), Matrix (>= 1.2-13), nlme (>=
##   3.1-124), rstan (>= 2.18.1), rstantools (>= 1.4.0),
##   shinystan (>= 2.3.0), stats, survival (>= 2.40.1), utils
## Suggests: betareg, data.table (>= 1.10.0), digest, gridExtra,
##   HSAUR3, knitr (>= 1.15.1), MASS, mgcv (>= 1.8-13),
##   rmarkdown, roxygen2, testthat (>= 1.0.2)
## LinkingTo: StanHeaders (>= 2.18.0), rstan (>= 2.18.1), BH (>=
##   1.66.0), Rcpp (>= 0.12.0), RcppEigen (>= 0.3.3.3.0)
## SystemRequirements: GNU make, pandoc (>= 1.12.3), pandoc-citeproc
## VignetteBuilder: knitr
## LazyData: true
## NeedsCompilation: yes
## URL: http://discourse.mc-stan.org, http://mc-stan.org/,
##   http://mc-stan.org/rstanarm/
## BugReports: https://github.com/stan-dev/rstanarm/issues
## RoxygenNote: 6.1.0
## Packaged: 2018-11-08 22:19:38 UTC; ben
## Author: Jonah Gabry [aut], Imad Ali [ctb], Sam Brilleman [ctb],

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##      Jacqueline Buros Novik [ctb] (R/stan_jm.R), AstraZeneca
##      [ctb] (R/stan_jm.R), Trustees of Columbia University [cph],
##      Simon Wood [cph] (R/stan_gamm4.R), R Core Deveopment Team
##      [cph] (R/stan_aov.R), Douglas Bates [cph] (R/pp_data.R),
##      Martin Maechler [cph] (R/pp_data.R), Ben Bolker [cph]
##      (R/pp_data.R), Steve Walker [cph] (R/pp_data.R), Brian
##      Ripley [cph] (R/stan_aov.R, R/stan_polr.R), William
##      Venables [cph] (R/stan_polr.R), Paul-Christian Burkner
##      [cph] (R/misc.R), Ben Goodrich [cre, aut]
## Maintainer: Ben Goodrich <benjamin.goodrich@columbia.edu>
## Repository: CRAN
## Date/Publication: 2018-11-10 16:30:02 UTC
## Built: R 3.6.1; x86_64-pc-linux-gnu; 2019-07-15 14:39:47 UTC; unix
##
## -- File: /usr/local/lib/R/site-library/rstanarm/Meta/package.rds
##
## [[8]]
## Package: Rcpp
## Title: Seamless R and C++ Integration
## Version: 1.0.1
## Date: 2019-03-16
## Author: Dirk Eddelbuettel, Romain Francois, JJ Allaire, Kevin
##        Ushey, Qiang Kou, Nathan Russell, Douglas Bates and John
##        Chambers
## Maintainer: Dirk Eddelbuettel <edd@debian.org>
## Description: The 'Rcpp' package provides R functions as well as
##             C++ classes which offer a seamless integration of R and
##             C++. Many R data types and objects can be mapped back and
##             forth to C++ equivalents which facilitates both writing of
##             new code as well as easier integration of third-party
##             libraries. Documentation about 'Rcpp' is provided by
##             several vignettes included in this package, via the 'Rcpp
##             Gallery' site at <http://gallery.rcpp.org>, the paper by
##             Eddelbuettel and Francois (2011,
##             <doi:10.18637/jss.v040.i08>), the book by Eddelbuettel
##             (2013, <doi:10.1007/978-1-4614-6868-4>) and the paper by
##             Eddelbuettel and Balamuta (2018,
##             <doi:10.1080/00031305.2017.1375990>); see
##             'citation("Rcpp")' for details.
## Depends: R (>= 3.0.0)
## Imports: methods, utils
## Suggests: RUnit, inline, rbenchmark, knitr, rmarkdown, pinp,
##           pkgKitten (>= 0.1.2)
## VignetteBuilder: knitr
## URL: http://www.rcpp.org,
##      http://dirk.eddelbuettel.com/code/rcpp.html,
##      https://github.com/RcppCore/Rcpp
## License: GPL (>= 2)
## BugReports: https://github.com/RcppCore/Rcpp/issues
## MailingList: Please send questions and comments regarding Rcpp to
##             rcpp-devel@lists.r-forge.r-project.org
## RoxygenNote: 6.0.1
## NeedsCompilation: yes
## Packaged: 2019-03-16 15:29:08.470813 UTC; edd

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## Repository: CRAN
## Date/Publication: 2019-03-17 07:15:10 UTC
## Built: R 3.6.1; x86_64-pc-linux-gnu; 2019-07-15 12:59:06 UTC; unix
##
## -- File: /usr/local/lib/R/site-library/Rcpp/Meta/package.rds
##
## [[9]]
## Package: forcats
## Title: Tools for Working with Categorical Variables (Factors)
## Version: 0.4.0
## Authors@R: c(person(given = "Hadley", family = "Wickham", role =
##   c("aut", "cre"), email = "hadley@rstudio.com"),
##   person(given = "RStudio", role = c("cph", "fnd")))
## Description: Helpers for reordering factor levels (including
##   moving specified levels to front, ordering by first
##   appearance, reversing, and randomly shuffling), and tools
##   for modifying factor levels (including collapsing rare
##   levels into other, 'anonymising', and manually 'recoding').
## License: GPL-3
## URL: http://forcats.tidyverse.org,
##   https://github.com/tidyverse/forcats
## BugReports: https://github.com/tidyverse/forcats/issues
## Depends: R (>= 3.1)
## Imports: ellipsis, magrittr, rlang, tibble
## Suggests: covr, ggplot2, testthat, readr, knitr, rmarkdown, dplyr
## Encoding: UTF-8
## LazyData: true
## RoxygenNote: 6.1.1
## VignetteBuilder: knitr
## NeedsCompilation: no
## Packaged: 2019-02-17 14:15:34 UTC; hadley
## Author: Hadley Wickham [aut, cre], RStudio [cph, fnd]
## Maintainer: Hadley Wickham <hadley@rstudio.com>
## Repository: CRAN
## Date/Publication: 2019-02-17 14:40:02 UTC
## Built: R 3.6.1; ; 2019-07-15 13:24:52 UTC; unix
##
## -- File: /usr/local/lib/R/site-library/forcats/Meta/package.rds
##
## [[10]]
## Package: stringr
## Title: Simple, Consistent Wrappers for Common String Operations
## Version: 1.4.0
## Authors@R: c(person(given = "Hadley", family = "Wickham", role =
##   c("aut", "cre", "cph"), email = "hadley@rstudio.com"),
##   person(given = "RStudio", role = c("cph", "fnd")))
## Description: A consistent, simple and easy to use set of wrappers
##   around the fantastic 'stringi' package. All function and
##   argument names (and positions) are consistent, all
##   functions deal with "NA"'s and zero length vectors in the
##   same way, and the output from one function is easy to feed
##   into the input of another.
## License: GPL-2 | file LICENSE
## URL: http://stringr.tidyverse.org,

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##           https://github.com/tidyverse/stringr
## BugReports: https://github.com/tidyverse/stringr/issues
## Depends: R (>= 3.1)
## Imports: glue (>= 1.2.0), magrittr, stringi (>= 1.1.7)
## Suggests: covr, htmltools, htmlwidgets, knitr, rmarkdown, testthat
## VignetteBuilder: knitr
## Encoding: UTF-8
## LazyData: true
## RoxygenNote: 6.1.1
## NeedsCompilation: no
## Packaged: 2019-02-09 16:03:19 UTC; hadley
## Author: Hadley Wickham [aut, cre, cph], RStudio [cph, fnd]
## Maintainer: Hadley Wickham <hadley@rstudio.com>
## Repository: CRAN
## Date/Publication: 2019-02-10 03:40:03 UTC
## Built: R 3.6.1; ; 2019-07-15 14:15:52 UTC; unix
##
## -- File: /usr/local/lib/R/site-library/stringr/Meta/package.rds
##
## [[11]]
## Type: Package
## Package: dplyr
## Title: A Grammar of Data Manipulation
## Version: 0.8.3
## Authors@R: c( person("Hadley", "Wickham", , "hadley@rstudio.com",
##           c("aut", "cre"), comment = c(ORCID =
##           "0000-0003-4757-117X")), person("Romain", "Fran\u00e7ois",
##           role = "aut", comment = c(ORCID = "0000-0002-2444-4226")),
##           person("Lionel", "Henry", role = "aut"), person("Kirill",
##           "M\u00fcller", role = "aut", comment = c(ORCID =
##           "0000-0002-1416-3412")), person("RStudio", role = c("cph",
##           "fnd")) )
## Description: A fast, consistent tool for working with data frame
##           like objects, both in memory and out of memory.
## License: MIT + file LICENSE
## URL: http://dplyr.tidyverse.org,
##           https://github.com/tidyverse/dplyr
## BugReports: https://github.com/tidyverse/dplyr/issues
## Depends: R (>= 3.2.0)
## Imports: assertthat (>= 0.2.0), glue (>= 1.3.0), magrittr (>=
##           1.5), methods, pkgconfig, R6, Rcpp (>= 1.0.1), rlang (>=
##           0.4.0), tibble (>= 2.0.0), tidyselect (>= 0.2.5), utils
## Suggests: bit64, callr, covr, crayon (>= 1.3.4), DBI, dbplyr,
##           dtplyr, ggplot2, hms, knitr, Lahman, lubridate, MASS, mgcv,
##           microbenchmark, nycflights13, rmarkdown, RMySQL,
##           RPostgreSQL, RSQLite, testthat, withr, broom, purrr, readr
## LinkingTo: BH, plogr (>= 0.2.0), Rcpp (>= 1.0.1)
## VignetteBuilder: knitr
## Encoding: UTF-8
## LazyData: yes
## RoxygenNote: 6.1.1
## NeedsCompilation: yes
## Packaged: 2019-07-04 05:04:15 UTC; romainfrancois
## Author: Hadley Wickham [aut, cre]

```

```

##      (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4757-117X>), Romain François
##      [aut] (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2444-4226>), Lionel
##      Henry [aut], Kirill Müller [aut]
##      (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1416-3412>), RStudio [cph,
##      fnd]
## Maintainer: Hadley Wickham <hadley@rstudio.com>
## Repository: CRAN
## Date/Publication: 2019-07-04 15:50:02 UTC
## Built: R 3.6.1; x86_64-pc-linux-gnu; 2019-07-15 14:26:41 UTC; unix
##
## -- File: /usr/local/lib/R/site-library/dplyr/Meta/package.rds
##
## [[12]]
## Package: purrr
## Title: Functional Programming Tools
## Version: 0.3.2
## Authors@R: c( person("Lionel", "Henry", , "lionel@rstudio.com",
##      c("aut", "cre")), person("Hadley", "Wickham", ,
##      "hadley@rstudio.com", "aut"), person("RStudio", role =
##      c("cph", "fnd")) )
## Description: A complete and consistent functional programming
##      toolkit for R.
## License: GPL-3 | file LICENSE
## URL: http://purrr.tidyverse.org,
##      https://github.com/tidyverse/purrr
## BugReports: https://github.com/tidyverse/purrr/issues
## Depends: R (>= 3.1)
## Imports: magrittr (>= 1.5), rlang (>= 0.3.1)
## Suggests: covr, crayon, dplyr (>= 0.7.8), knitr, rmarkdown,
##      testthat, tibble, tidycselect
## VignetteBuilder: knitr
## Encoding: UTF-8
## LazyData: true
## RoxygenNote: 6.1.1
## NeedsCompilation: yes
## Packaged: 2019-03-15 15:56:56 UTC; lionel
## Author: Lionel Henry [aut, cre], Hadley Wickham [aut], RStudio
##      [cph, fnd]
## Maintainer: Lionel Henry <lionel@rstudio.com>
## Repository: CRAN
## Date/Publication: 2019-03-15 18:20:02 UTC
## Built: R 3.6.1; x86_64-pc-linux-gnu; 2019-07-15 14:13:39 UTC; unix
##
## -- File: /usr/local/lib/R/site-library/purrr/Meta/package.rds
##
## [[13]]
## Package: readr
## Version: 1.3.1
## Title: Read Rectangular Text Data
## Description: The goal of 'readr' is to provide a fast and friendly
##      way to read rectangular data (like 'csv', 'tsv', and
##      'fwf'). It is designed to flexibly parse many types of data
##      found in the wild, while still cleanly failing when data
##      unexpectedly changes.

```

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## Authors@R: c( person("Hadley", "Wickham", , "hadley@rstudio.com",
##   "aut"), person("Jim", "Hester", ,
##   "james.hester@rstudio.com", c("aut", "cre")),
##   person("Romain", "Francois", role = "aut"), person("R Core
##   Team", role = "ctb", comment = "Date time code adapted from
##   R"), person("RStudio", role = c("cph", "fnd")),
##   person("Jukka", "Jylänki", role = c("ctb", "cph"), comment
##   = "grisu3 implementation"), person("Mikkel", "Jørgensen",
##   role = c("ctb", "cph"), comment = "grisu3 implementation"))
## Encoding: UTF-8
## Depends: R (>= 3.1)
## LinkingTo: Rcpp, BH
## Imports: Rcpp (>= 0.12.0.5), tibble, hms (>= 0.4.1), R6, clipr,
##   crayon, methods
## Suggests: curl, testthat, knitr, rmarkdown, stringi, covr,
##   spelling
## License: GPL (>= 2) | file LICENSE
## BugReports: https://github.com/tidyverse/readr/issues
## URL: http://readr.tidyverse.org,
##   https://github.com/tidyverse/readr
## VignetteBuilder: knitr
## RoxygenNote: 6.1.1
## SystemRequirements: GNU make
## Language: en-US
## NeedsCompilation: yes
## Packaged: 2018-12-20 16:06:40 UTC; jhester
## Author: Hadley Wickham [aut], Jim Hester [aut, cre], Romain
##   Francois [aut], R Core Team [ctb] (Date time code adapted
##   from R), RStudio [cph, fnd], Jukka Jylänki [ctb, cph]
##   (grisu3 implementation), Mikkel Jørgensen [ctb, cph]
##   (grisu3 implementation)
## Maintainer: Jim Hester <james.hester@rstudio.com>
## Repository: CRAN
## Date/Publication: 2018-12-21 09:40:02 UTC
## Built: R 3.6.1; x86_64-pc-linux-gnu; 2019-07-15 13:24:59 UTC; unix
##
## -- File: /usr/local/lib/R/site-library/readr/Meta/package.rds
##
## [[14]]
## Package: tidyr
## Title: Tidy Messy Data
## Version: 0.8.3.9000
## Authors@R: c(person(given = "Hadley", family = "Wickham", role =
##   c("aut", "cre"), email = "hadley@rstudio.com"),
##   person(given = "Lionel", family = "Henry", role = "aut",
##   email = "lionel@rstudio.com"), person(given = "RStudio",
##   role = "cph"))
## Description: tidyr helps to create tidy data, where each column is
##   a variable, each row is an observation, and each cell
##   contains a single value. tidyr contains tools for changing
##   the shape (pivoting) and hierarchy (nesting and unnesting)
##   of a dataset, as well as extracting values out of string
##   columns. It also includes tools for working with missing
##   values (both implicit and explicit).

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## License: MIT + file LICENSE
## URL: http://tidyr.tidyverse.org,
##       https://github.com/tidyverse/tidyr
## BugReports: https://github.com/tidyverse/tidyr/issues
## Depends: R (>= 3.1)
## Imports: dplyr (>= 0.7.0), ellipsis (>= 0.1.0), glue, magrittr,
##           purrr, Rcpp, rlang, stringi, tibble (>= 2.1.1), tidyselect
##           (>= 0.2.5), utils, vctrs (>= 0.2.0)
## Suggests: covr, jsonlite, knitr, repurrrsive, rmarkdown, readr,
##           testthat
## Remotes: jennybc/repurrrsive
## LinkingTo: Rcpp
## VignetteBuilder: knitr
## Encoding: UTF-8
## LazyData: true
## Roxygen: list(markdown = TRUE)
## RoxygenNote: 6.1.1
## RemoteType: github
## RemoteHost: api.github.com
## RemoteRepo: tidyr
## RemoteUsername: tidyverse
## RemoteRef: master
## RemoteSha: c6e291c1776fa2c4e69923062f2fe919d12ac400
## GithubRepo: tidyr
## GithubUsername: tidyverse
## GithubRef: master
## GithubSHA1: c6e291c1776fa2c4e69923062f2fe919d12ac400
## NeedsCompilation: yes
## Packaged: 2019-07-15 14:54:52 UTC; root
## Author: Hadley Wickham [aut, cre], Lionel Henry [aut], RStudio
##         [cph]
## Maintainer: Hadley Wickham <hadley@rstudio.com>
## Built: R 3.6.1; x86_64-pc-linux-gnu; 2019-07-15 14:54:53 UTC; unix
##
## -- File: /home/ben/R/x86_64-pc-linux-gnu-library/3.6/tidyr/Meta/package.rds
##
## [[15]]
## Package: tibble
## Title: Simple Data Frames
## Version: 2.1.3
## Authors@R: c( person("Kirill", "Müller", , "krlmlr+r@mailbox.org",
##                     c("aut", "cre")), person("Hadley", "Wickham", ,
##                     "hadley@rstudio.com", "aut"), person("Romain", "Francois",
##                     , "romain@r-enthusiasts.com", "ctb"), person("Jennifer",
##                     "Bryan", , "jenny@rstudio.com", "ctb"), person("RStudio",
##                     role = "cph") )
## Description: Provides a 'tbl_df' class (the 'tibble') that
##              provides stricter checking and better formatting than the
##              traditional data frame.
## License: MIT + file LICENSE
## URL: http://tibble.tidyverse.org/,
##       https://github.com/tidyverse/tibble
## BugReports: https://github.com/tidyverse/tibble/issues
## Depends: R (>= 3.1.0)

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## Imports: cli, crayon (>= 1.3.4), fansi (>= 0.4.0), methods, pillar
##           (>= 1.3.1), pkgconfig, rlang (>= 0.3.0), utils
## Suggests: bench, covr, dplyr, htmltools, import, knitr, mockr,
##           nycflights13, rmarkdown, testthat, withr
## VignetteBuilder: knitr
## Encoding: UTF-8
## LazyData: yes
## RoxygenNote: 6.1.1
## Collate: 'add.R' 'as_tibble.R' 'check-names.R' 'compat-lazyeval.R'
##           .....
## NeedsCompilation: yes
## Packaged: 2019-06-06 12:40:47 UTC; kirill
## Author: Kirill Müller [aut, cre], Hadley Wickham [aut], Romain
##         Francois [ctb], Jennifer Bryan [ctb], RStudio [cph]
## Maintainer: Kirill Müller <krlmlr+r@mailbox.org>
## Repository: CRAN
## Date/Publication: 2019-06-06 13:40:03 UTC
## Built: R 3.6.1; x86_64-pc-linux-gnu; 2019-07-15 13:22:58 UTC; unix
##
## -- File: /usr/local/lib/R/site-library/tibble/Meta/package.rds
##
## [[16]]
## Package: ggplot2
## Version: 3.2.0
## Title: Create Elegant Data Visualisations Using the Grammar of
##        Graphics
## Description: A system for 'declaratively' creating graphics, based
##              on "The Grammar of Graphics". You provide the data, tell
##              'ggplot2' how to map variables to aesthetics, what
##              graphical primitives to use, and it takes care of the
##              details.
## Authors@R: c( person("Hadley", "Wickham", , "hadley@rstudio.com",
##                      c("aut", "cre")), person("Winston", "Chang", , role =
##                      "aut"), person("Lionel", "Henry", , role = "aut"),
##                      person("Thomas Lin", "Pedersen", role = "aut"),
##                      person("Kohske", "Takahashi", role = "aut"),
##                      person("Claus", "Wilke", role = "aut"), person("Kara",
##                      "Woo", role = "aut"), person("Hiroaki", "Yutani", role =
##                      "aut"), person("RStudio", role = c("cph")) )
## Depends: R (>= 3.2)
## Imports: digest, grDevices, grid, gtable (>= 0.1.1), lazyeval,
##           MASS, mgcv, reshape2, rlang (>= 0.3.0), scales (>= 0.5.0),
##           stats, tibble, viridisLite, withr (>= 2.0.0)
## Suggests: covr, dplyr, ggplot2movies, hexbin, Hmisc, knitr,
##           lattice, mapproj, maps, maptools, multcomp, munsell, nlme,
##           profvis, quantreg, rgeos, rmarkdown, rpart, sf (>= 0.7-3),
##           svglite (>= 1.2.0.9001), testthat (>= 0.11.0), vdiff (>=
##           0.3.0)
## Enhances: sp
## License: GPL-2 | file LICENSE
## URL: http://ggplot2.tidyverse.org,
##       https://github.com/tidyverse/ggplot2
## BugReports: https://github.com/tidyverse/ggplot2/issues
## LazyData: true

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## Collate: 'ggproto.r' 'ggplot-global.R' 'aaa-.r' 'aes-calculated.r'
##      ....
## VignetteBuilder: knitr
## RoxygenNote: 6.1.1
## Encoding: UTF-8
## NeedsCompilation: no
## Packaged: 2019-06-13 19:32:10 UTC; thomas
## Author: Hadley Wickham [aut, cre], Winston Chang [aut], Lionel
##      Henry [aut], Thomas Lin Pedersen [aut], Kohske Takahashi
##      [aut], Claus Wilke [aut], Kara Woo [aut], Hiroaki Yutani
##      [aut], RStudio [cph]
## Maintainer: Hadley Wickham <hadley@rstudio.com>
## Repository: CRAN
## Date/Publication: 2019-06-16 14:00:03 UTC
## Built: R 3.6.1; ; 2019-07-15 14:28:37 UTC; unix
##
## -- File: /usr/local/lib/R/site-library/ggplot2/Meta/package.rds
##
## [[17]]
## Package: tidyverse
## Title: Easily Install and Load the 'Tidyverse'
## Version: 1.2.1
## Authors@R: c( person("Hadley", "Wickham", , "hadley@rstudio.com",
##      role = c("aut", "cre")), person("RStudio", role = c("cph",
##      "fnd")) )
## Description: The 'tidyverse' is a set of packages that work in
##      harmony because they share common data representations and
##      'API' design. This package is designed to make it easy to
##      install and load multiple 'tidyverse' packages in a single
##      step. Learn more about the 'tidyverse' at
##      <https://tidyverse.org>.
## License: GPL-3 | file LICENSE
## URL: http://tidyverse.tidyverse.org,
##      https://github.com/tidyverse/tidyverse
## BugReports: https://github.com/tidyverse/tidyverse/issues
## Imports: broom (>= 0.4.2), cli (>= 1.0.0), crayon (>= 1.3.4),
##      dplyr (>= 0.7.4), dbplyr (>= 1.1.0), forcats (>= 0.2.0),
##      ggplot2 (>= 2.2.1), haven (>= 1.1.0), hms (>= 0.3), httr
##      (>= 1.3.1), jsonlite (>= 1.5), lubridate (>= 1.7.1),
##      magrittr (>= 1.5), modelr (>= 0.1.1), purrr (>= 0.2.4),
##      readr (>= 1.1.1), readxl (>= 1.0.0), reprex (>= 0.1.1),
##      rlang (>= 0.1.4), rstudioapi (>= 0.7), rvest (>= 0.3.2),
##      stringr (>= 1.2.0), tibble (>= 1.3.4), tidyr (>= 0.7.2),
##      xml2 (>= 1.1.1)
## Suggests: feather (>= 0.3.1), knitr (>= 1.17), rmarkdown (>=
##      1.7.4)
## VignetteBuilder: knitr
## Encoding: UTF-8
## LazyData: true
## RoxygenNote: 6.0.1
## NeedsCompilation: no
## Packaged: 2017-11-14 00:57:48 UTC; hadley
## Author: Hadley Wickham [aut, cre], RStudio [cph, fnd]
## Maintainer: Hadley Wickham <hadley@rstudio.com>

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## Repository: CRAN
## Date/Publication: 2017-11-14 18:09:56 UTC
## Built: R 3.6.1; ; 2019-07-15 14:46:56 UTC; unix
##
## -- File: /usr/local/lib/R/site-library/tidyverse/Meta/package.rds
```